

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Analysis of leadership style, compensation and motivation on employee performance mediated by job satisfaction at the population Office and the Civil Registry of Medan City

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Abstract

This study aims to test and analyze the influence of leadership style, compensation and motivation on employee performance. Testing and analyzing the influence of leadership style, compensation, and motivation on employee performance mediated by Satisfaction at the Medan City Population and Civil Registration Office. This type of research is quantitative descriptive, the research sample is 85 ASN from the Civil Registry of Capil Regency, Medan City, and data analysis uses the SEM (structural equation modeling) method. Overall, from the results and discussions in the study, it was concluded that there was a positive and significant influence between leadership style, compensation and motivation on employee performance, and there was a positive and significant influence between leadership style, compensation, and motivation on employee performance mediated satisfaction at the Medan City Population and Civil Registration Office.

Keywords: Employee Performance; Satisfaction; Leadership style; Compensation; Motivation

1. Introduction

Quality human resources in the field they are engaged in need good leaders in terms of leadership to run the organization/government. A leader who has abilities in his field is very influential for the performance of employees to perform in accordance with the instructions given [1]. A leader's expertise in carrying out his duties to protect an organization or company will be a factor that can support an effective leadership process and create good work performance [2]. Leaders and their subordinates should be able to cooperate with each other and fill in each other's shortcomings in order to create a compact, cooperative and harmonious working climate in all parts. Success is the actualization of one's potential as well as an opportunity to meet the needs of life for an employee [3]. Meanwhile, for companies, success is a means to the growth and development of the company. Along with its development, companies often neglect the management of their human resources [4].

One of the considerations for employee productivity is fair compensation. Compensation is everything that employees receive in return for their work. The issue of compensation may be a confusing function of personnel management. Not only because compensation is one of the most complex tasks, but also one of the aspects that is meaningful for both employees and the organization [5]. The existence of compensation in the form of bonuses, gifts and awards will also have a positive impact on employees. Employees will feel motivated and enthusiastic in completing the assigned tasks and will appear encouraging employees to excel in their performance.

Motivation is the driving force that creates a person's passion so that they want to work together, work effectively and be integrated with all their efforts to achieve positive performance and satisfaction. So motivation questions how to

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direct the power and potential of their subordinates so that they want to work together productively, successfully achieve and realize the goals that have been determined [6]. In influencing, motivating, guiding, directing, and mobilizing human resources, in creating good performance, it is necessary to have a figure who has the right leadership. A leadership style that a leader who always tries to adapt to the situation and conditions of the organization, and is flexible in adjusting to the maturity of subordinates and the work environment. This is in accordance with the current global competition conditions that are always changing, so it is required to be more adaptive to the environment. Therefore, Leaders must be able to use the right leadership style so that employees can immediately improve employee performance.

Job satisfaction is a very important aspect in the work environment, both in the private and public sectors. Job satisfaction reflects an employee's level of satisfaction and happiness with their work, including factors such as work environment, salary, benefits, career development opportunities, and interpersonal relationships in the workplace. High job satisfaction is associated with various positive benefits, one of which is an increase in employee performance.

In creating effective employee performance, it is necessary to improve optimal work and be able to mobilize the potential resources owned by each employee, so that it can support the achievement of organizational goals and objectives. Success in achieving organizational plans and goals is the result of the performance of its employees. The performance of each member of the organization is directly related to the overall performance of the organization. With the achievement of organizational goals and objectives in a sustainable manner, it will have a positive impact on the development and progress of the organization in the future. Organizations are expected to pay attention to various factors that can affect employee performance, in which case the role of the organization is needed to increase motivation and support the creation of a conducive work environment. This will be useful to support the creation of effective and professional attitudes, behaviors and actions of each employee in completing work in accordance with their roles and responsibilities. Organizational leaders also need to pay attention to various other factors that can affect employee performance in supporting the achievement of organizational goals and objectives.

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Performance is one of the variables to find out how far the organization has achieved its goals and objectives. When viewed from the human resources approach, employee performance is an important factor as a determinant of whether the human resources owned by the organization have worked optimally in achieving the organization's goals and objectives, and will ultimately have an impact on the overall performance of the organization. Factors that affect employee performance include: leadership style, compensation, motivation, and satisfaction.

Based on the above background, the author is interested in conducting research entitled Analysis of Leadership Style, Compensation and Motivation for Employee Performance Mediated by Job Satisfaction at the Medan City Population and Civil Registration Office.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Leadership Style

According to [7], leadership is an effort to influence others to achieve goals that have been set well. Successful leadership depends on the right behaviors, skills, and actions, not on personal traits. According to [8], leadership style is behavior and strategy as a result of a combination of philosophy, skills, traits, attitudes, which are often applied by a leader in interacting with others, in making decisions, and in carrying out control activities. According to Miftah in (Siagian & Khair, 2018) states that leadership style is a norm of behavior used by a person when that person tries to influence the behavior of others or their subordinates.

Factors that affect leadership style according to [9], namely: 1) Communication. Have a clear strategy and communicate well to their subordinates, 2) Caring. Have a high level of concern for members and their work environment. 3) Motivating. Stimulate members to achieve the goals that have been set. 4) Maintain team cohesion. Creating a comfortable atmosphere and environment for all its members.

Indicators that can be used for leadership style include: 1) Traits, 2) Habits, 3) Temperament, 4) Character, 5) Personality

2.2. Compensation

According to [10] Compensation is everything that employees receive in return for their work. Compensation programs are also important for companies, as they reflect the organization's efforts to retain human resources. According to [10], Compensation is an award / reward for workers who have contributed to realizing their goals, through activities called work. Compensation in this case can be categorized into two major groups, namely direct compensation and indirect compensation.

Indicators for compensation according to [11], are as follows: a. Salary (sallary), b) Incentives, c) Bonuses, d) Working wages e) Premiums f) Treatment, g) Insurance Factors that affect compensation include the following [11]:

1. Productivity Any company wishes to obtain Profits, These profits can be in the form of material profits, as well as non-material profits. For this reason, companies must consider the productivity of their employees in their contribution to the company's profits.
2. Ability to Pay. To Pay The provision of compensation will depend on the company's ability to pay.
3. Willingness to Pay. To Pay The willingness to pay will affect the policy of providing compensation to its employees.
4. Demand. Labor A large number of workers in the job market will affect the compensation system.
5. Employee Organization. The existence of employee organizations will affect the compensation policy.
6. Various Regulations and Legislation. The better the government system, the better the legal system, including in the field of labor (employees) or employment

2.3. Motivation

According to [12] it is stated that motivation is the process of influencing or encouraging from the outside to a person or work group so that they want to carry out something that has been determined. Meanwhile, according to Liang Gie in Samsudin, motivation is the work done by managers in providing inspiration, enthusiasm and encouragement to others, in this case their employees, to take certain actions. The motivation that exists in a person will manifest a behavior that is directed towards the goal of achieving the goal of satisfaction. So motivation is not something that can be observed but is things that can be inferred to exist because of a behavior that appears. Motivation is the desire in a person that causes that person to act. Usually the person acts for a reason to achieve a certain goal. The approach to understanding work motivation is different, because the theories used are different so that they develop their own views and models [13]. Meanwhile, according to [14], motivation is a factor that encourages a person to do a certain activity, therefore motivation is often interpreted as a driving factor for a person's behavior to be able to change himself into what he wants.

The factors that affect motivation are:

1. Leadership Factor
2. Communication Factor
3. Needs Factor
4. Training Factor
5. Compensation Factor
6. Achievement Factor.

Indicators that affect motivation according to [13], namely:

1. Physical needs, shown by the provision of salaries, bonuses, transportation money, meals, housing facilities, and so on.
2. The need for a sense of security and safety, shown by occupational security and safety facilities, which include the existence of labor social security, health benefits, pension funds, work safety equipment, and accident insurance.

3. Social needs, shown by interacting with other people, including the need to be accepted in a group, the need to love, and be loved.
4. The need for awards, shown by recognition and appreciation based on the abilities possessed, the need to be respected and appreciated by other employees and leaders for their work achievements.
5. The need for self-realization, aimed at the nature of challenging and interesting work, where employees will exert their abilities and potential. In meeting this need, organizations or companies can do it, by providing education and training

2.4. Satisfaction

Job satisfaction may be related to psychological factors. A number of personal variables also determine the level of employee job satisfaction, which is included in this category according to [15] are gender factors, age factors, education factors, personality factors, and expectation factors. According to [16], factors that affect job satisfaction.

According to [16], the factors that affect job satisfaction are:

1. Work conditions, namely job satisfaction that arises from the need to work is fulfilled and a supportive environment.
2. Regulations, culture and characteristics that exist in the organization that can support the work.
3. Compensation from work that is balanced with workWorking conditions, namely job satisfaction that arises from the need to work is fulfilled and a supportive environment.
4. Regulations, culture and characteristics that exist in the organization that can support the work.
5. Compensation from his work that is balanced with the work done.
6. Work efficiency, which is the satisfaction that arises from working according to their abilities.
7. Promotion opportunities, which are where there is an opportunity to get an award for one's work achievements such as promotions and higher duties and accompanied by a salary increase.
8. Colleagues, which are relationships that are well established within the organization so that there are no obstacles in doing work.

According to [17]in [18], the indicators of job satisfaction are:

1. The job itself
2. The job's suitability and personality
3. Wages and promotions
4. The attitude of colleagues, supervisors, superiors
5. Working environment conditions.

2.5. Employee Performance

Employee performance according to [19] is a description of work results in the form of achievements in the implementation of tasks obtained by workers both individually and in groups in line with rules, authority, as well as morals and ethics. There are three factors used to measure employee performance:

- Workmanship quality
- Quantity of work;
- Punctuality

According to [20], there are several performance criteria indicators that can be used to measure employee performance, including the following:

1. Quantity (number)
2. Time (period)
3. Cost emphasis
4. Supervision
5. Individual relationships

Employee performance must always be at a high level in order to provide quality results and in line with the goals that have been set. As a result, there is a great need to overcome employee performance problems. Departing from the context mentioned above, the researcher plans to conduct a study on how well employees perform roles that affect leadership styles.

Based on the aspects described above, a conceptual framework of the research is made as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework of the Research

3. Research methods

3.1. Types of Research

The type of research used by the researcher is quantitative research [21] quantitative research can be interpreted as a method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research on a certain population or sample, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses. This type of quantitative research is carried out to create a research that aims to adapt a research.

3.2. Research Location and Research Time

The location of the research was carried out at the Medan City Population and Civil Registration Office. The research time was carried out for 3 months.

3.3. Population and Sample

Population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined by the researcher to be studied and then drawn conclusions [21] The population and sample in this study are employees who work at the Medan City ducapil office which is directly used as a sample, namely 85

3.4. Research Data Sources

The data source used in this study is primary data.

3.5. Operational Definition of Research Variables

Table 1 Operational Definition of Variables

Types of Variables	Definition	Indicator
Leadership Style (X1)	Leadership style is behavior and strategy as a result of a combination of philosophy, skills, traits, attitudes, which a leader often applies in interacting with others, in making decisions, and in carrying out control activities. [8]	1) Characteristic 2) Habits 3) Temperamen 4) Character 5) Personality [8]
Compensation (X2)	Compensation is everything that employees receive in return for their work. Compensation programs are also important for companies, as they reflect the organization's efforts to retain human resources [10]	1) Gaji (sallary) 2) Incentives 3) Bonus 4) Labor wages 5) Prizes 6) Treatment 7) Asurans [10]
Motivation (X3)	Motivation is the process of influencing or encouraging from the outside against a person or work group so that they want to carry out something that has been set [12]	1)Physical needs, 2)The need for a sense of security and Safety 3) Social needs 4). Need for rewards 5).The need for self-realization, [12]
Kepuasan (Z1)	Job satisfaction is a working condition, namely job satisfaction that arises from the need to work is fulfilled and a supportive environment [16]	1)The work itself. 2) Suitability of work with personality. 3) Wages and promotions. 4) The attitude of colleagues, supervisors, superiors. 5)Working environment conditions. [16]
Employee Performance (Y)	An overview of work results in the form of achievements in the implementation of tasks obtained by workers both individually and in groups in line with rules, authority, as well as morals and ethics [19]	1) quantity (quantity), 2) time (period), 3) cost suppression, 4) supervision, and 5) Individual relationships [19]

Source: Researcher, 2024

4. Result

In this research, the first test carried out was the analysis of *the outer model (measurement model)*. There are two components in the validity test, namely the convergence test and the discrimination test. The validity of convergence was assessed through *an average variance extracted (AVE)* score of > 0.5 and *a loading factor* value > 0.7 . The validity of the crime was tested by *cross-loading*. The reliability test was determined using *Cronbach's alpha* > 0.7 and *composite reliability* > 0.7 .

Table 2 Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and average variance extracted

Variable	Item Indikator	Factor loading	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability	AVE	Conclusion
Leadership Style (X1)	GKP1	0.947	0.959	0.968	0.859	Reliable
	GKP2	0.935				
	GKP3	0.887				
	GKP4	0.917				
	GKP5	0.949				
Compensation (X2)	KPI1	0.909	0.966	0.972	0.832	Reliable
	KPI2	0.936				
	KPI3	0.869				
	KPI4	0.948				
	KPI5	0.945				
	KPI6	0.884				
	KPI7	0.892				
Motivation (X3)	MTV1	0.904	0.946	0.959	0.824	Reliable
	MTV2	0.906				
	MTV3	0.880				
	MTV4	0.937				
	MTV5	0.911				
Satisfaction (Z)	KPS 1	0.939	0.973	0.979	0.903	
	KPS 2	0.959				
	KPS 3	0.968				
	KPS 4	0.897				
	KPS 5	0.969				
Employee Performance (Y)	KPW1	0.909	0.971	0.977	0.824	Reliable
	KPW2	0.968				
	KPW3	0.969				
	KPW4	0.958				
	KPW5	0.945				

Source: Primary Data Processed by SmartPLS (2024)

The factor loading score obtained based on Table 2 is more than 0.70, which means that it shows the reliability of the indicator measuring the online purchase decision process. Cronbach's alpha and composite values. reliability greater than 0.70, proving that the five variables are said to be reliable. Meanwhile, the AVE score > 0.5, proving that each variable was declared valid. The cross-loading value with its construct is used to test the validity of discrimination. In order to evaluate the validity of discrimination, an additional method that can be applied is to compare the average variance extracted (AVE) score along with the correlation between the construct and other constructs.

Table 3 Discrimination validity test results-Fornell Larcker Criterium

	Compensation	Employment Performance	Leadership Style	Motivation	Satisfaction
Compensation	0.912				
Employment Performance	0.934	0.947			
Leadership Style	0.947	0.919	0.927		
Motivation	0.951	0.939	0.956	0.908	
Satisfaction	0.958	0.940	0.952	0.961	0.950

Based on the results of Table 3, *Big Ramadan Sale, service quality, online customer review, trust, and online purchase decision process* obtained an AVE value of > 0.5, so it was declared to have passed the discrimination validity test. It can be said that variable measurement indicators have been proven to be valid in terms of *discriminant validity*. It can be concluded that the data model of this study meets the good criteria. After passing the validity and reliability test, the next stage is to evaluate *the inner model* through *coefficient determination (R2)* and *the coefficient path test*. The magnitude of the influence given by independent variables on other variables can be analyzed with R-square.

Table 4 Result R-square

	R-square(R2)	R-square adjusted
Satisfaction (Z)	0.947	0.945
Employee Performance (Y)	0.905	0.901

In Table 4, a Z value of 0.945 (94.5%) was obtained which was influenced by aspects of leadership style, compensation, and motivation. Meanwhile, employee performance was influenced by aspects of leadership style, compensation, and motivation by 0.901 (90.1%).

Source: Primary data processed by SmartPLS (2024)

Figure 2 Results of the bootstrapp technique coefficient path test

Tabel 5 Hasil uji *path coefficient* Direct

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>Sample Mean (M)</i>	<i>Standard deviation (STDEV)</i>	<i>T-statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Leadership Style (X1) → Employee Performance Y	0.084	0.090	0.111	4.757	0.009
Leadership Style (X1) → Satisfaction Z	0.579	0.580	0.103	5.634	0.007
Compensation (X2) → Kinerja Pegawai Y	0.182	0.185	0.094	3.935	0.004
Compensation (X2) → (Z) Satisfaction	0.282	0.282	0.101	2.802	0.008
Satisfaction (Z) → Employee Performance Y	0.648	0.640	0.100	6.508	0.032
Motivation X3 → Satisfaction Z	0.375	0.370	0.083	4.540	0.011
Motivasi X3 → Employee Performance Y	0.183	0.182	0.075	2.440	0.010

Tabel 6 Hasil uji *path coefficient* In - Direct

	<i>Original sample (O)</i>	<i>Sample mean (M)</i>	<i>Standard deviation (STDEV)</i>	<i>T-statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Leadership Style (X1) → Z Satisfaction Employee Performance Y	0.084	0.090	0.111	4.757	0.002
Compensation (X2) → Satisfaction Employee Performance Y	0.074	0.690	0.125	4.238	0.006
Motivasi (X3) → Satisfaction Employee Performance	0.579	0.580	0.103	5.634	0.003

Based on table 5, the leadership style gets t-statistics 4.757 higher than t-table (1.65) and gets a p-value of 0.000 less than 0.05. Thus, leadership style significantly affects satisfaction, so H1 is accepted. Leadership Style obtained a t-statistics value of 5.634 higher than t-table (1.65) and a p-value of 0.000 greater than 0.05. It can be said that leadership style significantly affects employee performance, so H2 is not accepted. The compensation gets a t-statistics value of 3.935 higher than the t-table (1.65) and a p-value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05. It was concluded that compensation significantly affected the employee's performance, then H3 was accepted. obtained a t-statistics value of 2.802 higher than t-table (1.65) and a p-value of 0.005 less than 0.05. It was concluded that compensation significantly affected employee performance, hence H4 was accepted. Motivation obtained a t-statistics value of 6.508 higher than t-table (1.65) and a p-value of 0.000 greater than 0.05. This proves that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The satisfaction obtained a t-statistics value of 2.767 higher than the t-table (1.65) and a p-value of 0.006 was less than 0.05. This proves that satisfaction can mediate the influence of leadership style on employee performance. obtained a t-statistics value of 4.540 higher than t-table (1.65) and a p-value of 0.000 less than 0.05. This proves that satisfaction is able to mediate the influence of compensation on employee performance. The satisfaction obtained a t-statistics value of 2.440 higher than the t-table (1.65) and a p-value of 0.015 was less than 0.05. This proves that satisfaction is able to mediate the influence of motivation on employee performance.

5. Discussion

Based on the results of the first hypothesis test, leadership style has a significant effect on satisfaction, as evidenced by the acquisition of p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. The influence of leadership style on job satisfaction is an important topic in human resource management and organizational psychology. Autocratic Leadership: Tends to give less autonomy to employees, which can reduce job satisfaction. Employees may feel devalued and less involved in decision-making. Participatory Leadership Encourages employee involvement in the decision-making process. This style often results in higher job satisfaction, as employees feel heard and valued. Transformational Leadership: Motivates and inspires employees to achieve common goals. This style can increase job satisfaction because it creates a positive environment and supports personal development.

Based on the results of the hypothesis testing, the two competencies have a significant effect on satisfaction, as evidenced by the acquisition of p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. Competence includes the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to perform tasks well. High competence is often associated with good performance. Employees who have high competence tend to show better performance. Good performance can increase job satisfaction, as employees feel successful and recognized for their contributions. Good competence increases employee confidence in carrying out tasks. When employees feel capable, they tend to feel more satisfied with their jobs. Competent employees have more opportunities for career development and promotion. Opportunities to grow and advance in a career can increase job satisfaction.

Based on the analysis of the third hypothesis, motivation has a significant effect on employee performance, as evidenced by the acquisition of p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. This is because The influence of motivation on job satisfaction is a crucial topic in human resource management. Motivation is an internal or external impulse that influences a person's behavior to achieve a specific goal. A person's level of motivation can have a big effect on performance and job satisfaction. Motivated employees tend to feel more satisfied with their jobs. They feel excited to perform tasks and achieve goals. Conversely, unmotivated employees may feel frustrated and dissatisfied with their jobs, which can lead to decreased performance. Motivated employees tend to feel more satisfied with their jobs. They feel excited to perform tasks and achieve goals. Conversely, unmotivated employees may feel frustrated and dissatisfied with their jobs, which can lead to decreased performance.

Based on the analysis of the fourth hypothesis, motivation has a significant effect on employee performance, as evidenced by the acquisition of p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. This is because Employees who feel satisfied with their jobs tend to be more motivated to work hard and achieve organizational goals. Satisfaction creates the drive to give your best. Job satisfaction is often related to employee engagement. Satisfied employees are more likely to be actively involved in tasks and projects, which can increase efficiency and productivity. Employees who feel satisfied tend to experience lower levels of stress. A positive and supportive work environment can improve mental and physical health, which contributes to better performance. High job satisfaction can reduce employee turnover rates. Employees who stay in the organization can improve the stability and overall performance of the team.

Based on the analysis of the fifth hypothesis, leadership style on employee performance has a significant effect on employee performance, as evidenced by the acquisition of p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. This is because the leadership style applied by a leader has a great influence on employee performance. Leaders who are able to create a positive work environment, involve the team in decision-making, and provide the necessary support can improve employee motivation, engagement, and overall performance. Therefore, it is important for organizations to choose and develop a leadership style that fits their culture and goals

Based on the analysis of the sixth hypothesis, compensation for employee performance has a significant effect on employee performance, as evidenced by the acquisition of p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. This is because employees who receive fair and competitive compensation tend to be more motivated to work hard. They feel valued, which can increase productivity. Bonuses, benefits, and other incentives can encourage employees to achieve their set goals and targets. Employees who are satisfied with their salary and benefits tend to be more satisfied with their jobs overall. This satisfaction is directly related to improved performance. Good compensation can reduce turnover rates, so employees who stay in the company can provide better performance.

Based on the analysis of the seventh hypothesis, the influence of motivation on employee performance has a significant effect on employee performance, as evidenced by the acquisition of p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. This is because motivated employees tend to be more productive. They have the drive to complete tasks well and on time, which contributes to better work outcomes. Motivated employees bring positive energy to their work, which can improve efficiency and work output. Motivated employees feel more emotionally attached to their work. This involvement often results in a higher

commitment to duties and responsibilities. Motivated employees are more likely to actively participate in team discussions, collaboration, and initiatives.

Based on the analysis of the eighth hypothesis, the influence of leadership style on satisfaction-mediated employee performance is evidenced by the acquisition of p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. This is because the influence of leadership style on employee performance mediated by job satisfaction is an interesting concept in management studies. Inspirational leaders can improve employee performance by motivating them to reach their best potential. These leaders typically create a clear vision and inspire the team to achieve it. Leaders who involve employees in decision-making can improve performance through increased employee engagement and commitment to their tasks. Job satisfaction can act as a mediator between leadership style and employee performance. Good leaders can create a positive work environment, which increases employee job satisfaction.

Based on the analysis of the ninth hypothesis, the effect of compensation on satisfaction-mediated employee performance is evidenced by the acquisition of p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. This is because the influence of compensation on employee performance mediated by other factors, such as job satisfaction or motivation, is an important aspect of human resource management. Fair salaries, bonuses, and benefits can increase employee motivation to work harder and achieve organizational goals. Awards, recognition, and opportunities for career development also play a role in improving performance.

Based on the analysis of the tenth hypothesis, the effect of compensation on satisfaction-mediated employee performance is evidenced by the acquisition of p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. This is because the influence of motivation on employee performance through job satisfaction is an important concept in human resource management. Motivated employees tend to work more productively and efficiently. They have the drive to achieve goals and complete tasks well. When employees feel motivated, they will strive more to achieve better results, which directly affects their performance. High motivation often contributes to increased job satisfaction. When employees feel motivated, they tend to feel more satisfied with their work. High motivation often contributes to increased job satisfaction. When employees feel motivated, they tend to feel more satisfied with their work. Employees who are satisfied with their work are more likely to be committed, engaged, and give their best, which has a positive impact on their performance.

6. Conclusions

The results of research and discussion, leadership style, compensation and motivation are based on a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Leadership style, compensation, and motivation have a positive and significant effect on the employee performance process through satisfaction. Leadership style has a significant influence on employee performance, and job satisfaction acts as a mediator in this relationship. Leaders who are able to create a supportive and positive work environment can increase job satisfaction, which in turn will improve employee performance. Therefore, it is important for organizations to implement an effective leadership style and focus on improving job satisfaction in order to achieve optimal performance. Compensation has an important influence on employee performance, and factors such as job satisfaction and motivation play a role as mediators in this relationship. By increasing fair and relevant compensation, organizations can increase employee satisfaction and motivation, which in turn will improve overall performance. Therefore, it is important for management to pay attention to the compensation aspect in human resource management strategies. Motivation has a significant influence on employee performance, and job satisfaction acts as a mediator in this relationship. Motivated employees tend to be more satisfied with their jobs, which in turn improves performance. Therefore, it is important for organizations to create strategies that increase employee motivation and satisfaction in order to achieve optimal performance.

High motivation increases job satisfaction, which in turn improves performance. Employees who work well and feel satisfied tend to be more motivated to continue contributing

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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